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Differences in company projects - a way of inspiring educational design for employability

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1 INTRODUCTION

The skills expected of tomorrow's engineers and demanded by accrediting institutions and employers point clearly in the direction of more generic and employability competencies in addition to the technical knowledge, skills and competences. Reports have identified a major problem in the transition from education to work and characterised this problem as a skills gap [1].

Research indicates that employers have not been satisfied with the graduates and it has been pointed out that ways to change the curriculum is to integrate work related situations [2]–[4]. Especially project work in collaboration with industry has been one of the ways to foster employability competencies, e.g. by letting students work with authentic real life problems in a company context [5]–[6]. Most often, engineering students are doing this by working on projects involving company collaboration in one or more of the project phases from problem identification to problem solving.

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In general, collaboration between two different types of organisations and cultures will always create challenges because of different practices and norms. Internally at the university, such types of collaboration might therefore be challenging both for the curriculum design and for the practice as academic facilitator. On the other hand, research indicates increase of students' motivation for learning when there is an end-user or customer for their projects and that the engineering students feel more ready for entering into the labour market [7]. Internationally, engineering projects and engineering practice become a more dominant element of the engineering curriculum [8].

The increased focus on types of company collaboration in the engineering education society, and the increased student-company interaction in company projects, creates a need for curriculum design that includes external stakeholders – especially companies. Not much research exists to inspire the integration of company project in curriculum design, and therefore, this study contributes to this field by addressing the following research question:

What types of collaboration can be identified between companies and universities for student projects and what impact will the different types of collaboration have for curriculum design?

In the following, we will address this question by presenting results from a new study on student-company collaboration in students' project work. This study on student-company collaboration in engineering education is supported by the Danish Anniversary Fond for Technical Engineering 1980. Aalborg University serve as case, due to its strong tradition for student-company collaboration, as noted by the IRIS Group [9].

2 METHODOLOGY

The overall purpose of the study was to identify if very different practices occur for how students collaborate with the companies in their projects and by the results to provide inspiration for educational designers when they consider strategies for change to integrate company projects further in the curricula.

Therefore, qualitative methods were applied in order to gain an understanding of the nature of the collaboration. The methodology for the study was a combination of qualitative content analyses of curricula and interviews with involved stakeholders. The content analyses included screening of curricula from the School of Engineering and Science in order to identify how the collaboration with companies was described at the formal level. The interviews were semi-structured interviews to include openness and to catch the different nature of the collaboration. In total, 16 were conducted, of which 12 interviews have been carried out in person and 4 by telephone.

The aim was to include a broad range of expertise, including educational designers and practitioners from university staff, students, employers as well as researchers. The 16 interviews were distributed with 8 interviews with university staff, 2 interviews with students, 4 interviews with employers and 2 interviews with researchers. The employers were selected by a screening of the AAU database for projects with specific focus on company-projects.

The interviews were partly transcribed for a thematic cross-cutting analysis of collaboration patterns.

3 FINDINGS

From the analyses of the curricula descriptions, it became clear that company-student collaboration in projects was more implicit mentioned – and much more as a possibility and not a requirement. From this analysis, it was not possible to distinguish requests on different types of company-student collaboration.

The interviews, however, showed significant differences in the role that the company plays in the students' projects and thereby also the type of collaboration taking place. Four roles were distinguished, at which the company respectively serves as an informant, a case, a client or a partner in the project.

As the pattern of diversity emerged, it became clear that the different types of roles were not mutually exclusive, but interrelated and mutually inclusive, as shown in figure 1. There was a clear difference in the role of the company as an informant and a case, but of course the information is the first step of both a case and a more shared collaboration and partnership.

Fig. 1. Model in the different types of company relations in company projects.
The arrow indicates the line of progression.

In the following, we elaborate on the roles in a step-wise fashion. We are moving from the inside to the outside of figure 1, from the informant to the partner role, and as we do so, the scope of the student-company projects is gradually expanded.

2.1 The company as an informant

If a project is to be characterised as a company project, it will include interaction with one or more companies, and students have to at least have a contact to the company making them able to integrate first hand knowledge into their project – in this case, the company acts as

an informant. It can be that the students seek information from one or more companies to understand a problem, a practice or a technology. In any case, the staff interviewed stresses the importance of providing the students with the opportunity to interact with companies, e.g. by arranging company visits, guest lectures or providing access to the research networks. Furthermore, they also emphasise the importance of having students trained in approaching and collecting information from business relations. As noted by one of the university staff members (Staff 1, Personal interview, September, 2017):

“It is really not the technical competences that matter, when we find that this is a good student to send into a company, as much as the ability to manage oneself in a business environment. Having the sense of how to behave, what questions to ask and which not to ask, what you prepare for in advance and what you have to ask for. It is about having a sense of propriety”

The ability to redraw information from a company relation is, furthermore, underlined by the following quote (Staff 2, Personal interview, September, 2017):

“Some students are better at in-depth questioning than others and they are able to draw out valuable experiences. Others are a bit quick, getting too focused on what they want to do in their projects themselves, and they do get the same benefit. The most beneficial process typically happens when the students asks openly and humbly to study what the real problem is, and what the company knows and what is not known.”

The ability to approach and collect data from companies and other informants can, therefore, be seen as a basic inquiry for company-student projects, and therefore, it can be argued that this also should be integrated into the curriculum as a learning objective in the very beginning of the study. For the documentation of the learning outcomes of this type of student-company collaboration, students can include the data from the company as empirical material and include a reflection on the student-company collaboration as part of the methodological reflection in their project reports.

2.2 The company as a case

The next level including the company as a case includes a higher and continuous level of interaction. This means a stronger commitment from the company and thereby also a stronger company interest for the outcome. In the case-perspective, the company gains an outsiders view on company processes, which can be very valuable. As one of the company partners noted (Employer 1, Telephone interview, September, 2017):

“Regarding our own current innovation tasks, we receive new, fresh ideas to include in further internal or external research tasks”.

Another company partner, who at that time worked together with a student on a case-project, supplements with a statement about the value of having a student work in a case-based approach (Employer 2, Personal interview, September, 2017):

“It simply provides new energy to the organisations, when a young person steps in with engagement and curiosity in the way we are doing things. We get some new perspectives, and at the same time we get an opportunity to impact the project along the way”.

Even though the company partner can impact the project along the way, there are no clear expectations on the outcome of the project, which lowers the pressure on student performance, and therefore, it can be argued that these projects can take place from early on in the curriculum, and, of course, with increasing depth throughout the study.

For the documentation of learning outcomes of this type of student-company collaboration, students can document the case-study as part of a project report, and furthermore, several of the interviewed stress the importance of providing the company more targeted feedback, e.g. by making an oral presentation at the company to report on the case-study.

2.3 The company as a client

If the company acts as a client or customer, the company raises a specific need or problem that they want the students to address. In this case, students still have to get overview of business processes and understand the particularities of the company, although the case-analysis might not be as in-depth as in a case-project. Compared to the case-projects, the client projects, furthermore, provide some clearer expectations from the company regarding the output, and, typically, a certain degree of progression in technical competences is needed in order for students to cope with these types of projects and provide unique solutions of value for the company. A student directed learning environment will, however, imply that the students are free to shape the project considering their own interest, as this student explains (Student 1, Personal interview, September, 2017):

“When the company is a client in a project it is never 100%. It has never been like that they wanted a certain kind of product, and then we just have to deliver it. We have a high degree of ownership of the project.”

It is a negotiation between the learning objectives and the company objectives, the student interests and the interests of the companies, and also between the academic communities and the business communities. This is exemplified by the following quote (Staff 1, Personal interview, September, 2017):

“It is a challenge to balance company requests with the learning objective. The easy answer is that it is all about the students, and student learning, and that the benefit for the company is just a side-product. But in reality, it is not completely like that as we really want the companies to have some value in return, and it is also much more fun for the students when this happens. In sum we are very interested in creating value for our collaborative partners, because then they will also continue to work with us. It is a balance.”

It can also be argued that this situation of being in the middle of mutual and maybe sometimes conflicting interests, in fact will help the student to gain important competences in balancing different needs in projects as well as in the innovation of new products.

For the documentation of the learning outcomes of this type of student-company collaboration, students might document their outcome by a prototype as a supplement to the project report and oral presentation targeted the company. Furthermore, the company as well as the university might also be interested in a more detailed process-report considering the developments.

In the School of Engineering and Science at Aalborg University, the guideline for internship requests that student include a reflection in the documentation of their project considering [10]:

- a description of the external organisation, including structure and areas of work
- an overview of the work areas in which the student has been involved
- a report on the actual work performed by the student, an analysis of how the student has benefited from the traineeship academically, professionally and socially
- the student's experience with the traineeship, including any possible suggestions for changing the curriculum, procedures etc.
- a reflection on the knowledge exchange between the external organisation and the study programme
- an evaluation of the learning outcome of the traineeship.

In this way, the student-company collaboration is captured by letting the student reflect on the type of company and the type of interaction, and also the learning outcome as well as the learning process.

2.4 The company as a partner

Last but not least, examples do exist of students working on projects together with companies to the extent where they share, not only the same engagement in the project, but also the same practice. The student and the company have established what Lave & Wenger [11] have called a community of practise, where the participants, driven by a shared engagement, share information and experiences.

If the students are to work together with the company in a community of practice, they have to understand the core interest and engagement embedded in the role as a client, which the company brings into the project. But it also works the other way around. The company has to understand where the students are coming from and respect that they have to live up to the intended learning outcomes stated in the curricula, as note by one of the staff members (Staff 3, September, 2017):

“The good company, in terms of creating the most optimal conditions for an internship, is a company, which is aware of the intended learning outcomes, which the students have to live up to. This is for examples the case when we collaborate with some of our former students”

In some projects, students engage in several company projects during internships (Staff 3, Personal interview, September, 2017). In other projects, the representatives from the company join the group for analysis or experiments, as in the following example (Staff 2, Personal interview, September, 2017):

“In this project about recuperation of phosphor in waste-water, the students was involved in some experiments at a pilot-test-facility, and the other company partners was also involved, and made some measures, and then the results were discussed. It was also discussed which samples that should be taken and how they should be analysed. The students and company partners have several meetings along the way.”

These types of communities of practice can be considered the highest order of learning for employability, and for some students close to graduation, a successful community of practice

can be the first step to employment. Students are not only being present, observing and interacting. They are also being trusted to enter a company community and engage in co-constructions as illustrated by the following quote (Staff 4, Personal interview, September, 2017):

“Especially one year, it was so obvious, when we had a gathered seminar to finalise the semester that the students came with a whole different charisma and attitude than before they have been in internship. A lot of self-confidence was added - they were changed from being students to being professionals. They learn, and sometimes because they just have to, to be outgoing, stand on their own feet and trust in themselves – yes, I can do it – it provides self confidence”.

This process of becoming able to “stand on their own feet” and trust in themselves seems however to be gradual, as explained by a student (Student 1, Personal interview, September, 2017):

“In the beginning, at the first and second semester, the supervisor was present at least at the first meeting with the company, acted like a chair of the meeting and was like the one who took care of our interests and learning. That was really nice at the first semesters, but it felt like an enormous vote of confidence when the supervisor suddenly said: I do not have to go with you. You can manage yourself”

This quote moves the discussion of progression and appropriation to the scaffolding of students. It is a matter of gradually letting go and providing the students the opportunities to take the lead, as elaborated by de Graaff et al [12].

But even though we might agree on the importance of this development, the learning outcomes are however hard to grasp and put into words for students as well as assessors. This however does not mean that it cannot be done. Our study especially point to the diary as a way for students to be able to capture the personal developments, as noted in the following quote (Staff 3, Personal interview, September, 2017):

“Students are recommended to write a diary during the project, to capture the relations and reflect on the experience in relation to their personal role, for example by asking: what surprised me, what interest was in play, how did I contribute to the praxis unfolding, how do I consider the process from a more critical perspective, etc.”

Being, is a personal matter, and therefore there is also an issue of willingness from the student to share with their supervisor their personal reflections in the diary (Staff 5, Personal interview, September, 2017). However, the diary holds a potential to gather data on-going to a level of detail that will enable student to exemplify and document personal growth in the context of a company community of practice.

4 CONCLUDING REMARKS

In this paper, we reported from experiences with student-company collaboration supporting students' project work, we have presented four different types of student-company collaborations, which is presented in figure 1.

As the patterns of diversity emerged, it became clear that the different types of collaboration were not mutually exclusive; rather they could be seen as building blocks in progression from projects where the company was merely acting as an informant to projects where students worked closely together with the company in a community of practice.

We hope that the different roles of the company in the company projects, as informants, cases, clients or partners, can inspire curriculum designer to make the progression of learning outcomes of company projects more planned, explicit and documented.

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